

EVALUATION OF OXIDATION BEHAVIOR OF UHTC COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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Keywords: UHTC, C/UHTC, Oxidation behavior

ABSTRACT

C/ZrB₂-SiC-ZrC (C/ZSZ) is one of the candidate materials for thermal protection systems of aerospace application. This material indicates excellent recession and oxidation resistance at high temperature above 1700°C. In the present study, oxidation behavior of C/ZSZ was investigated using an oxyhydrogen torch to optimize composition. After the ablation test at 1800°C, the cross-section was observed using SEM-EDX. The matrix of heated surface converted into a ZrO₂-SiO₂ layer. This oxide layer became denser with higher volume content of ZrC. On the other hand, the increase of ZrC induced the excessive ZrO₂ that is cause by low oxidation resistance. Based on these results, we determined that the best composition was ZrB₂:ZrC = 2:3 within the range of this study.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced silicon carbide matrix (C/SiC) and SiC fiber reinforced SiC matrix (SiC/SiC) composites have been used as thermal protection systems for aerospace application [1, 2]. SiC forms a protective condensed-phase SiO₂ at high temperature, which is called passive oxidation. However, active oxidation forming volatile oxides immediately decreases oxidation resistance of SiC above 1600°C [3].

Carbon fiber reinforced ultra high temperature ceramics (C/UHTCs) matrix composites have been focused on apply of thermal protection system used above 1600°C such as leading edges of hypersonic vehicles [1, 2]. Carbides, borides and nitrides of transition metals with high melting points, e.g. ZrC, ZrB₂, HfB₂, and TaC are classified into UHTCs [4]. Several researchers reported that the binary system material of ZrB₂-SiC exhibits good oxidation resistance above 1600°C [1, 5, 6]. On the other hand, recession resistance of these materials was insufficient under high-speed flow condition because binary system including SiC such as ZrB₂-SiC formed a porous oxide layer inside the material [7].

Zhang et al reported that the recession resistance of ternary system of C/ZrB₂-SiC-ZrC (C/ZSZ) was better than that of C/ZrB₂-SiC [8]. They indicated the ZrO₂ generated from ZrC was effective to improve the recession resistance of C/UHTC. In order to optimize the composition of ZrB₂:SiC:ZrC systems, the detail of their oxidation behavior related to the high recession resistance should be investigated.

The purpose of this study is the clarification of recession and oxidation mechanisms of C/ZSZ. As a first step, we observed oxidation behavior of ZSZ, which has different composition under static oxidation condition. Then, we also examined the recession and the oxidation resistance of C/ZSZ in different composition under dynamic heating condition using an oxyhydrogen torch. Furthermore, C/SiC and C/ZrB₂-SiC were also prepared and tested for reference.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 Materials

ZSZ and ZrB₂-SiC were fabricated by Spark Plasma Sintering (SPS-520S, Sumitomo Coal Mining, JAPAN) process. ZrB₂, SiC, and ZrC powder were mixed using a planetary ball milling. The average particle diameter was 2~3 μm for ZrB₂ and ZrC, 0.5 μm for SiC. The powder mixtures were sintered in Ar at 1950°C for 2 minutes under pressure of 50 MPa with heating rate of 130 °C/minute. The ZSZ has four different composition as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Composition of matrix materials.

samples	V _{ZrB₂} (vol%)	V _{SiC} (vol%)	V _{ZrC} (vol%)	
ZSZ	No.1	20	16	64
	No.2	34	16	50
	No.3	50	16	34
	No.4	64	16	20
ZrB ₂ -SiC	84	16	0	

The fabrication procedure of the C/ZSZ is shown in Fig. 1. Slurry including phenol resin, ZrB₂ and ZrC was applied plain woven carbon cloth (T-300, TORAY, JAPAN). These fiber cloths with slurry were laminated and pressed at 150°C under 0.8 MPa. C/C-ZrB₂-ZrC was fabricated from these preforms by carbonization at 1000°C in inert atmosphere and sintering at 1500°C in vacuum. Then, the molten Si was infiltrated into C/C-ZrB₂-ZrC to convert carbon matrix into SiC at 1500°C in vacuum. Table 2 shows composition, bulk density and open porosity of the composite materials. C/ZSZ, having four different compositions, were prepared by different slurry mixing ratio of ZrB₂ and ZrC. C/SiC and C/ZrB₂-SiC were also fabricated by using SiC and ZrB₂ slurry respectively to compare with the behaviors and properties of C/ZSZ.

Fig. 1: Fabrication procedure of C/ZSZ.

Table 2: Composition of the composite materials.

samples	slurry mixing ratio (vol%ZrC)		bulk density (g/cm ³)	open porosity (%)	
	ZrB ₂	ZrC			
C/ZSZ	No.1	25	75	2.3	5.6
	No.2	40	60	2.3	6.3
	No.3	60	40	2.2	6.5
	No.4	75	25	2.2	7.1
C/ZrB ₂ -SiC	100	0	2.2	7.2	
C/SiC	-	-	2.1	3.5	

Fig. 2 (a) shows the typical cross-section of as-fabricated C/ZSZ. In the matrix, ZrB₂, SiC and ZrC particle were distributed homogeneously. As shown in Fig. 2 (b), some voids, transverse cracks and residual Si were observed. This photograph also shows that carbon fibers located at outermost of fiber bundles reacted with Si to form SiC.

Fig. 2: (a) Typical cross-section of C/ZSZ, (b) high magnification image of (a).

2.2 Tests and characterization

The matrix specimen were oxidized under static oxidation condition using an IR image furnace (IR-QP1-4S, YONEKURA, JAPAN). After heating up to 1700°C in Ar, an iso-thermal oxidation test was carried out in Ar-2.0%O₂ at 1700°C for 10 minutes. Ar-2.0%O₂ gas flow rate was 1.0 l/min. A disk-shaped specimen with a diameter of 10 mm and a thickness of 1.5 mm was used. After the test, a cross-section of the specimen was polished and observed by a scanning electron microscope (S-4200, HITACHI, JAPAN). Elemental analysis was also carried out using energy dispersive x-ray analysis (EDX, AMETEK, USA).

The composite materials were oxidized under dynamic heating condition using an oxyhydrogen torch system as shown in Fig. 3. The ablation test was carried out in air atmosphere at 1800°C for 10 minutes. The dimensions of rectangular specimen were 30 mm × 30 mm × 5 mm for C/ZSZ and C/ZrB₂-SiC or 30 mm × 30 mm × 3 mm for C/SiC. The specimens were fixed to support jig so that the specimen surface was vertical to torch nozzle. The distance from the nozzle tip to the specimen surface was 70 mm. The surface temperature of a specimen was measured by a pyrometer (IR-AHU, CHINO, JAPAN). Emissivity was set to 0.90. After ablation tests, surface and cross-section of specimens were observed by an optical microscope (VHX500, KEYENCE, JAPAN) and SEM with EDX. The specimen thickness was also measured by a laser displacement sensor to determine linear recession thickness. The measuring area was 26 mm × 26 mm and the measuring interval was 260 μm so that the measuring points were 10,000 points. The linear recession thickness was determined by subtracting the specimen thickness after oxidation from the original one. The non-oxidized thickness was also measured from the optical image. The oxidized thickness was also determined by subtracting the non-oxide thickness from the original one.

Fig. 3: Schematic drawing of ablation test system.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Oxidation behavior of the ZSZ and ZrB₂-SiC

Fig. 4 shows SEM-EDX observation results for the cross-section of ZrB₂-SiC after oxidation test under static oxidation condition. There is a ZrO₂-SiO₂ layer on the surface layer. SiO₂ on the surface has lower oxygen diffusion coefficient and preserves material from further oxidation [8, 9, 10]. A SiC-depleted layer, which does not contain oxide and SiC, is observed in ZrB₂-SiC as shown in Fig. 4. Fig. 5 also shows thickness of oxide and oxidized layers measured from SEM-EDX image. Under low oxygen partial pressure, the SiC-depleted layer is formed more actively [11]. However, there are no SiC-depleted layer in ZSZ. This indicates that the recession resistance of ZSZ is higher than that of ZrB₂-SiC. ZrC is oxidized firstly in matrix under low oxygen partial pressure at 1700°C [12]. Therefore, it is assumed that the SiC-depleted layer become denser with higher volume content of ZrC.

The oxidation resistance of ZSZ No.4 is almost equal to that of ZrB₂-SiC. However, the oxidation resistance of the other ZSZs is lower than that of ZrB₂-SiC. The increase of ZrC induces the excessive ZrO₂ that is cause of the low oxidation resistance because ZrO₂ has higher oxygen diffusion coefficient [9, 10].

Fig. 4: SEM-EDX image of ZrB₂-SiC after the oxidation test.

Fig. 5: Thickness of oxide and oxidized layer of matrix materials.

3.2 Oxidation behavior of the composite materials

Fig. 6 shows the surface of the composite materials after the ablation test. Some kind of oxides such as ZrO_2 , SiO_2 , $ZrSiO_4$ and borosilicate were probably produced on the surface layer [13, 14]. The white region (Fig. 6-A as indicated by arrows) and clear glassy region (Fig. 6-B as indicated by arrows) are observed in C/ZSZ and C/ZrB₂-SiC. On the other hands, only clear glassy region is observed in C/SiC. Therefore it is assumed that the white region is mainly ZrO_2 and the clear glassy region is mainly SiO_2 .

Fig. 7 shows SEM-EDX image of C/ZSZ (No. 3). The oxide layers were clearly identified by element mapping image. As we expected, a ZrO_2 - SiO_2 layer was formed on the surface. In the next layer, there is a SiO_2 -rich layer including some voids formed by oxidation of carbon fiber. The oxide is not observed under the SiO_2 -rich layer.

Fig. 6: Surface of the composite materials after ablation test
(a) C/ZSZ (No. 3), (b) C/ZrB₂-SiC, (c) C/SiC, (d-f) high magnification image of (a-c).

Fig. 7: SEM-EDX image of C/ZSZ after ablation test.

3.3 The recession thickness and the damaged thickness of the composite materials

Fig. 8 shows the recession thickness and the oxidized thickness of the composite materials with four different composition. As the increase of ZrC content in the matrix, the recession and the oxidation resistance are improved. The improvement of the recession resistance originates from the densification of the ZrO_2 - SiO_2 layer. This oxidation behavior is based on that of matrix. The dense ZrO_2 - SiO_2 layer efficiently protects a SiO_2 layer from mechanical erosion, and leads to good oxidation resistance. The recession and the oxidation resistance of C/ZSZ except for No.4 is higher than that of C/ ZrB_2 -SiC and C/SiC. The oxidation resistance of No.1 is lower than No.2 and 3. This is due to excessive ZrO_2 in the same way as the only matrix. For these reasons, we determined that the best composition was No.2 (60 vol%ZrC) within the range of this study.

Fig. 8: The recession thickness and the oxidized thickness of the composite materials.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The matrix materials oxidized under static oxidation condition formed the ZrO_2 - SiO_2 protective oxidation layer. The SiC-depleted layer was observed only in ZrB_2 -SiC. In the case of ZSZ, it is assumed that the SiC-depleted layer become denser with higher volume content of ZrC because the oxidation rate of ZrC is highest in matrix. This mechanism improves the recession resistance of ZSZ. C/ZSZ ablated by an oxyhydrogen torch exhibited excellent recession and oxidation resistance compared with C/ ZrB_2 -SiC and C/SiC. The recession resistance of C/ZSZ results from the dense ZrO_2 - SiO_2 layer formed at the surface of C/ZSZ. This dense ZrO_2 - SiO_2 layer efficiently protected SiO_2 -rich layer from mechanical erosion. Therefore the oxidation resistance of C/ZSZ was improved. We determined that the best composition was ZrB_2 :ZrC = 2:3 within the range of this study.

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